

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

HIGH HORIZONS – D1.4

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	Data management plan (year 1)
Deliverable number	D1.4
WP number	WP1
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Lead beneficiary	UGent
Type	R: Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU: Public
Due date	30 November 2022

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Draft created by Beneficiary UGent (21 October 2022)
Version 0.2	Draft revised by HIGH Horizons partners & including feedback from UGent data steward (16 November 2022)
Version 0.3	Draft incorporating feedback from HIGH Horizons partners and UGent data steward (25 November 2022)
Version 0.4	Draft revised by Scientific Coordinator (28 November 2022)
Version 1.0	First year data management plan (28 November 2022)

TABLE OF CONTENT

List of tables	2
1 Data summary	4
1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?.....	4
1.2 What types and formats of data and other research outputs will the project generate or re-use?	4
1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project? .	8
1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?.....	8
1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?.....	9
1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	13
2 FAIR data	13
2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	13
2.2 FAIR data: Making data accessible.....	15
2.3 FAIR data: Making data interoperable.....	17
2.4 FAIR data: Increase data re-use	18
3 Other research outputs	19
3.1 Do you have any additional information that was not addressed in previous sections, which you wish to provide regarding other research outputs that are generated or re-used throughout the project? ...	19
4 Allocation of resources	19
4.1 What will the costs be for making data and other research outputs FAIR in your project?	19
4.2 How will these be covered?.....	20
4.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	20
4.4 How will long term preservation be ensured?	20
5 Data security	21
5.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security?	21
5.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	21
6 Ethics	22
6.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?.....	22
6.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?.....	23
7 Other issues	23
7.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?.....	23

List of tables

Table 1: Overview of data re-use and/or generation by country	4
Table 2: Data re-use by HIGH Horizons	5
Table 3: Data generation by HIGH Horizons	6
Table 4: Metadata list	14

HIGH Horizons: data management plan

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline.be

Action title: Heat Indicators for Global Health (HIGH Horizons): Monitoring, Early Warning Systems and health facility interventions for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children and health workers

Funder: European Commission (Horizon)

Grant number / URL: 101057843

Start date: 01-09-2022

End date: 31-08-2026

Project abstract:

The HIGH Horizons project addresses several critical knowledge gaps around the quantification and monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of heat exposure on maternal, newborn and child health. We quantify and monitor direct and indirect health impacts of extreme heat on pregnant women, infants and health workers, test a personalised Early Warning System, and implement integrated adaptation-mitigation actions in health facilities. A smartphone app (ClimApp-MCH) will deliver warnings and setting-specific messages, co-designed locally. The app will be evaluated in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe, both among 200 mothers and infants, from antepartum through 12 months of infant age, and among 60 health workers. Modifications to health facilities will be co-designed and modelled to reduce health workers' heat exposure and limit facilities' carbon emissions. Health worker outcomes and facility emissions will be compared pre-and post-intervention. We engage relevant stakeholders in conducting the research and disseminating project findings, prioritising country partners, EU, and global policy makers and leveraging existing networks.

DMP version number: V1.0

Version based on input from original proposal and the Description of the Action + modifications/comments partners DTU, WHRI, UNI GRAZ, AKHS and ULUND (track changes accepted and suggestions incorporated) + feedback UGent data steward integrated where possible.

This version contains boxes in grey with actions to be taken for the next version.

The management plan will be updated continuously, and will be submitted again in month 24 of the HIGH Horizons project.

Date: 28 November 2022

1 Data summary

1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

Yes, existing data will be reused and (re)analysed, mainly within the context of WP2 which focuses on assessing the health impacts of climate change exposures. Examples of re-use of existing data(sets) are:

- Data from existing databases of environmental factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, air pollution and vegetation index) and health data routinely collected in health facilities will be curated to establish a long-term data platform for HIGH Horizons:
 - Existing databases of environmental factors to be considered include Copernicus and Galileo/EGNOS for satellite-based earth observations, positioning, navigation, and related timing data and services; reanalysis of datasets i.e. ERA5, JRA, NOAA. Also, CHIRTS and CHIRPS downscaled reanalysis for temperature and precipitation and soil moisture; CMIP6 for climate projections data; and National Met Offices.
 - Swedish and Italian birth register data and data from health facilities in East Africa (using the electronic health records from the health care system) and across one district and one sub-district in South Africa will be re-used to determine heat-health impacts by using time series and machine learning methods.

The database generated will be used to quantify and monitor heat impacts by applying time series or longitudinal spatiotemporal and data science models to document the impacts of heat, air pollution, and other environmental exposures on maternal, neonatal and child health (MNCH) outcomes. The set-up and update of this environmental-health database is a deliverable (month 8 and month 36).

- A systematic review of the impacts of heat exposure on MNCH outcomes and adaptive interventions to reduce impacts in pregnant and postpartum women and infants will be conducted using several databases (PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Google Scholar).

More details about the re-use of data in 1.5.

1.2 What types and formats of data and other research outputs will the project generate or re-use?

Datasets from Italy, Kenya, South Africa and Sweden will be re-used for predictive modelling and climate change attribution. Own data will be generated in the four countries participating in the HIGH Horizons project: Kenya, South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe. See table 1 for an overview.

Table 1: Overview of data re-use and/or generation by country

Country	DATA RE-USE	MAINLY DATA GENERATION		
	Data analysis for assessment of heat-health impacts (WP2)	EWS for Pregnant Women & Health Workers (WP3)	Facility Adaptation* (WP4 & 5)	Facility Mitigation** (WP4 & 5)
Italy	Yes	No	No	No
Kenya	Yes	No	No	Yes
South Africa	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sweden	Yes	Yes	No	No
Zimbabwe	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

* Facility Adaptation is to reduce heat/temperature in the facilities, e.g., fans, air conditioners.

** Facility Mitigation is to reduce greenhouse gases from facilities, e.g., solar panels, reducing emissions from waste.

1.2.1 Re-use of (secondary) data and other research outputs (DR)

Table 2: Data re-use by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Open sharing
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation							
DR 2.1	Database(s) of environmental factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, air pollution, and vegetation index)	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv) netcdf (.nc)	Raw, processed and published data	No	Yes
DR 2.2	Database(s) of Swedish and Italian birth register data	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	Yes	No
DR 2.3	Database of electronic health records from South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	Yes	No
DR 2.4	Spreadsheet with updated systematic literature review	Numerical & textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Published data	No	Yes
DR 2.5	Text document with updated systematic literature review	Textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	PDF/A (.pdf)	Published data	No	Yes
DR 2.6	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline)	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No
DR 2.7	Spreadsheet with carbon emissions in health facilities	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw processed data	No	No
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions							
DR 3.1	Spreadsheet with indoor and outdoor temperature (plus local weather files)	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv) TMY	Raw, processed and published data	No	Yes
DR 3.2	Algorithms/scripts from the original ClimApp software application	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking	x	x	No	Yes
WP4 - Implement monitoring mechanisms, Early Warning Systems, and adaptation and mitigation interventions in health facilities							
	(no re-use of data)						
WP5 - Evaluate the surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions, including cost-effectiveness							
DR 5.1	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (endline)	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No
DR 5.2	Spreadsheet with cost and financial data from health facilities	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw and processed data	No	No
DR 5.3	Spreadsheet with energy performance of cooling interventions in health care facilities	Numerical data	Calculated/simulated	CSV (.csv)	Raw and processed data	No	No

1.2.2 Generation of (primary) data and other research outputs (DG)

Table 3: Data generation by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Open sharing
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation							
DG 2.1	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature in the health facilities and personal temperature of the health workers	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No
DG 2.2	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline)	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 2.3	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted in the health facilities (baseline)	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 2.4	Questionnaire about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline)	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 2.5	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline)	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 2.6	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (baseline)	Audiovisual & textual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 2.7	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG2.6	Textual & audiovisual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp) .txt	Processed data	Yes	No
DG 2.8	Predictive and attributive modelling , applying data science methods	Numerical & categorical data	Data science methods	x	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	Yes
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions							
DG 3.1	Images from the Photovoice sub-study	Audiovisual data	Observational	JPEG (.jpeg)	Raw data	No	Yes
DG 3.2	Spreadsheet with indoor and outdoor temperature based on installed temperature monitors	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv) TMY	Raw, processed and published data	No	No
DG 3.3	Database with characteristics of the EWS users and their thermal exposure when using the ClimApp ¹	Numerical & categorical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 3.4	Algorithms/scripts of the EWS/ClimApp-MCH for pregnant women, postpartum women, infants and health workers	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking	x	x	No	Yes
DG 3.5	Thermal modelling and cost modelling techniques to inform selection of the building modification	Numerical & categorical data	Data science methods	x	Raw, processed and published data	No	Yes

¹ When ClimApp users agree to submit their data through the app, the heat exposure data and their responses such thermal perception will be collected. These responses and personal information (age, weight, height, GPS location to connect to local weather forecast, heat acclimatization, etc.) are sensitive.

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Open sharing
WP4 - Implement monitoring mechanisms, Early Warning Systems, and adaptation and mitigation interventions in health facilities							
DG 4.1	Audio recordings of semi-structured interviews with pregnant women and health workers about socio-demographics, heat exposure, heat impacts and adaptive measures, and the economic burden of heat-related stress (baseline)	Textual + Audiovisual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 4.2	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG4.1 and DG4.2	Textual & audiovisual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp) .txt	Processed data	Yes	No
WP5 - Evaluate the surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions, including cost-effectiveness							
DG 5.1	Questionnaire about EWS acceptability and usability, and on uptake of messages and related interventions (both by women during their pregnancy and one year postpartum and by health workers)	Numerical & textual data	Survey	paper sheet CSV (.csv) .txt	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.2	Spreadsheet with household expenditure data of the pregnant and postpartum women (baseline & endline)	Numerical data	Survey	paper sheet CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.3	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (endline)	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.4	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of work environment and activities conducted in the health facilities (endline)	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.5	Questionnaire about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel (baseline), administered by the health workers themselves (endline)	Numerical & textual data	Survey	delimited text CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.6	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (endline)	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.7	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (endline)	Audiovisual & textual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No
DG 5.8	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG5.7	Textual & audiovisual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp) .txt	Processed data	Yes	No

1.2.3 Describe what other research outputs will be collected, generated or re-used in the project (if applicable)

Other research outputs of HIGH Horizons include the software developed for the smartphone application ClimApp-MCH [see algorithms and scripts in table 3 – DG3.4] and the prediction and attribution modelling to assess the heat-health impacts [see models in table 3 – DG2.8]. These will be described in more detail in section 3.

As far as physical outputs are concerned: the urine samples of the health workers won't be collected, only the results of the dipstick test [see spreadsheets in table 3 – DG 2.5 & DG 5.6].

1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Both data re-use and data generation will support the assessment of the direct and indirect impacts of heat exposure on health, e.g.:

- Data will be re-used for retrospective analyses to measure and predict the population-level impacts of heat on maternal, newborn, and child health (MNCH), which in turn will inform the selection of priority indicators on the impacts of heat exposure on MNCH and the design and development of the surveillance system (Objective 1), an Early Warning System that provides individualized information to the users (Objective 2), and the facility adaptation and mitigation interventions (Objective 3).
- New data will be generated for prospective analyses and evaluation of the HIGH Horizons project, including the surveillance system, the EWS, and evaluation of the adaptation-mitigation interventions in health facilities.

More details about the purposes of data generation and re-use in 1.5.

1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

HIGH Horizons will produce a large amount of data and we estimate that we will at least generate and re-use data with a size of at least 200 GB.

- Data re-use: Depends on approval and interoperability to re-use the datasets; the expected size of the datasets will become clearer in the first project year.
- Data generation: e.g.,
 - The cohort size and period are limited (600 pregnant and postpartum women and 60 health workers during one year or maximum 18 months); data size is expected to be around 100 MB;
 - The 72 in-depth interviews with health workers and health facility, district and regional managers, at baseline and endline, will be audio recorded. If interviews last one hour on average, we estimate to generate at least 11.5 GB (= 72 participants & 1 hour x 2 interviews (baseline and endline) x 80 MB per interview).

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add more detailed estimates of the data to be re-used and generated.

1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Data re-use (see table 2)

As listed in 1.2, several datasets will be (re-)used to develop a **data platform with environmental factors and health data** (WP2).

- **Existing databases of environmental factors** [see DR2.1 in table 2], e.g., temperature, humidity, air pollution, and vegetation index), such as:
 - Copernicus and Galileo/EGNOS for satellite-based earth observations, positioning, navigation, and related timing data and services;
 - Reanalysis of datasets i.e. ERA5, JRA, NOAA. Also, CHIRTS and CHIRPS downscaled reanalysis for temperature and precipitation and soil moisture ([Soil moisture gridded data from 1978 to present \(copernicus.eu\)](#))
 - CMIP6 for climate projections data.
 - [Current weather and forecast – OpenWeatherMap](#)
 - National Met Offices
 - *Sweden*: In the Swedish site, we have already developed a multi-stage methodology based on a machine learning - random forests - to estimate PM (10, 2.5 and 2.5-10), NO₂, O₃ and ambient air temperature with high temporal (daily) and spatial (1 km²) resolution across the whole of the country. The data are drawn from multiple sources, including satellites, dispersion models, land cover, meteorology, and population data;
 - *Italy*: The Italian site (Lazio region) has a similar database, which was developed by the same team who constructed the Swedish database;
 - *Kenya, Tanzania, South Africa & Zimbabwe*: we (re-)use supplementary weather data from an external data source, i.e. the Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO) service.
 - Spatiotemporal machine learning techniques will incorporate data from monitoring stations, satellite Land Surface Temperature, meteorological reanalysis data, and land-use predictors (vegetation indexes, climate zones, and land cover features) and link these with population-based health and socio-demographic data.
 - For use with the EWS, meteorological data are extracted and computed from the Open Weather Map API based on the user's GPS location. The data consists of air temperature (°C), wind speed at 2 and 10 meter high (m/s), humidity (%), cloud coverage (%) and solar radiation (W/m²) [see DR3.1 in table 2].
- **Health data routinely collected (HMIS) in Italy, Sweden, Kenya, South Africa** [see DR2.2 & DR2.3 in table 2]:
 - *Italy*: Lazio Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (CEDAP), approximately 40,000 births per year;
 - *Sweden*: nationwide population register consisting of all MNCH health outcomes countrywide from 2014 onwards, approximately 100,000 births per year;
 - *Kenya*: data from routine electronic medical records in facilities that are run by AKHS, one of the largest health facility networks in East Africa. Data are extracted from the Care system, the AKDN (Aga Khan Development Network) delivery tool, and manual reports in the facilities;

- *South Africa*: electronic system data from one health district (Tshwane) and one sub-district in Johannesburg (Region F), which includes several large hospitals; e.g., in the Rahima Moosa Mother and Child Hospital site data on paediatric admissions dates back to the early 2000s and provides information on more than 16,000 paediatric admissions, and more than 17,000 births annually.

Within WP2, systematic reviews of the impacts of heat exposure on maternal and child health and adaptation-mitigation interventions will be updated in years 1 and 3 of the HIGH Horizons project to summarize any new evidence [see DR2.4 & DR2.5 in table 2]. The team will use the findings of the systematic reviews already completed by consortium partners (e.g., WHO, WHC).

To be done in next version of the DMP:

- Add digital object identifiers of (re-used) databases.

Data generation (see table 3)

Health worker impact [DG2.1 to DG2.8 & DG5.3 to DG5.8]

To build an accurate picture of heat and other exposures in the study sites (WP2), we will measure temperature and humidity in the health facilities in Sweden (n=4), South Africa (n=2), and Zimbabwe (n=2):

- Five health workers in each health facility will be requested to wear a personal temperature monitor during the hottest month of the year;
- Digital temperature sensors will be installed on an inside wall of selected health facilities and a ventilated outdoor structure close to each facility. The devices will collect temperature data at 10-minute intervals, and a LoRaWAN network will communicate and collect data from the sensors, using mobile data networks. Data will be stored on an online platform that will ensure continuous monitoring and access to the data on a real-time basis. Indoor heat exposure will be assessed according to American Society of Heating, Air conditioning & Refrigeration Engineers, US (ASHRAE) standards.

Design, implementation and evaluation of Early Warning System

- For the co-design of messages and infographics for the EWS (WP3), **Photovoice** will be applied by ten pregnant women, ten postpartum women and ten health workers in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe [see DG3.1].
- Cohort 1: 600 pregnant and postpartum women (>18 years old) with their infants (birth to age one year) to test the ClimApp EWS (Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe)
 - Per country, 200 women will be recruited from antenatal care clinics and will be followed until their infants are 12 months old;
 - Women will complete a **semi-structured interview at baseline**, including questions on socio-demographics, heat exposure, heat impacts and adaptive measures, and the economic burden of heat-related stress [see DG4.2 & DG4.3].
 - The **ClimApp** serves as tool for providing heat-health warnings, but also as a mobile tool for data collection from the participants. The app can predict individualized heat exposure, provide heat stress warnings (2-4 levels of heat warnings) and advice, and collect users' responses.
 - After childbirth the women will enter salient information about their child on the app, and warnings and messaging relevant to postpartum women and infants will be provided;

- Data collection includes real-time heat exposure and responses from women (self-reported thermal perception, and symptoms of thirst and skin wetness), allowing for further fine-tuning of the individual thresholds [DG3.2 & DG3.3];
 - We will also provide a set of questions to women on the app and request that she enters her responses directly into the app. The questions will cover EWS acceptability and usability, care-seeking practices, and childcare practices, such as the number of times they breastfed their child, and thermal discomfort during breastfeeding in hot periods [see DG5.1];
 - Data on **health expenditure** will be collected from the women, at baseline (enrolment) and once the infant is 12 months old.
- Cohort 2: 60 health workers active in maternal and child health services to test the ClimApp EWS (Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe)
 - Per country 20 MCH health workers will be recruited
 - Health workers will complete a **semi-structured interview at baseline**, including questions on socio-demographics, heat exposure, heat impacts and adaptive measures [see DG4.2 & DG4.3].
 - The **ClimApp** serves as a tool for providing heat-health warnings, but also as a mobile tool for data collection from the participants:
 - Data collection includes real-time heat exposure and responses from health workers (self-reported thermal perception, and symptoms of thirst and skin wetness), allowing for further fine-tuning of the individual thresholds;
 - Health workers will also answer questions about EWS acceptability and usability in the app [see DG5.1].

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add details on the online platform for temperature monitoring (e.g. remote management of the digital temperature sensors, topping of the mobile data,...).

Data re-use and generation (see tables 2 and 3)

Carbon emission measurement

For the measurement of carbon emissions in 2 health facilities each in *Kenya*, South Africa, and Zimbabwe, data will be collected from the health facilities for input into the **AKHS carbon footprinting tool** [see DR2.7 in table 2]. This Excel based tool for health facilities emissions assessment covers Scope 1, 2, and 3 greenhouse gas emissions, including supply chains. Along all levels, areas specific to the health care sector, such as anaesthetic gases and respiratory inhalers, are covered. The table below shows the required data that will be collected. Countries will collect and store data themselves. AKHS to compile quarterly consolidated data and submit in SharePoint.

- Note: Sweden/KI may also consider using the tool, but as this was not promised in the Description of the Action, we leave it out for now.

Data required

		AHEAD	
		ACA Knowledge Development Network	
Water	Volumes of water used		
Refrigerants	Kg of refrigerants held in, or used (cooling systems)		
Anaesthetic Gases	Numbers of bottles, cylinders or weight of anaesthetics used		
Inhalers	Number of Inhalers dispensed or prescribed		
Services	Amount spent on different types of products or services		
Suppliers	Amount spend with different suppliers		

Health worker impact

For the assessments of heat impacts on the well-being, health, and productivity of health workers and their provision of quality care (which will inform the co-design of health facility adaptive-mitigation interventions in WP3 and which will establish the baseline for the evaluation of the health facility interventions in WP4 and WP5), we will generate and (re-)use data. These data will be developed through a **mixed methods approach**, with a total of 72 health workers (15 from each of the four facilities in Zimbabwe and South Africa and 12 from the 4 ANC clinics in Sweden) [DG2.1 to DG2.8 & DG5.3 to DG5.8]. We will use a quasi-experimental design with a before-after component, with

1. Participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted by the health workers in the relevant clinics or wards;
2. Time Motion study, specifically adapted to the MNCH health care context, to systematically estimate and characterise health workers' productivity, workflow, and provision of quality care using quantitative data;
3. Self-administered survey questionnaire about the health workers' well-being (WHO Well-being Index for Health Workers tool), psychological status (perceived stress scale, and GAD-7 questionnaire for anxiety), perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel;
4. Collect urine sample for testing of health worker's urine osmolarity, a commonly used biomarker of hydration status;
5. Qualitative in-depth interviews with a smaller group of health workers, and health facility, district and regional managers (N=10-15 in Zimbabwe and South African sites, and approximately 3 per site in Sweden) to gain critical contextual information central to the development of strategies and interventions in each setting;
6. Routine health services and human resources data will be extracted from registers and health information systems in health facilities in Sweden (n=4), South Africa (n=2) and Zimbabwe (n=2) [see DR2.6 in table 2]. These data will cover the past 4-5 years and include information on the quality of clinical care, service utilisation and, if possible, to estimate absences and reasons for absence among MNCH health care workers during and outside periods of extreme heat.

ClimApp-MCH & scripts

The ClimApp-MCH will start from the current ClimApp scripts and software code [see DR3.2 in table 2], and will modify this Early Warning System for heat stress warning of women during pregnancy and postpartum, infants up to 1 years of age, and health workers in MNCH facilities [see DG3.4 & DG3.5 in table 3].

Cost-consequence analyses of the adaptation strategies

For the cost-consequence and cost-benefit analyses of the adaptation strategies (WP5) implemented in facilities in Sweden, South Africa, and Zimbabwe, we will extract and collect cost and financial data from the health facilities [see DR5.1 and DR5.2], and collect household expenditure data of the pregnant and postpartum women (baseline & endline) [see DG5.2 in table 3].

1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

- Researchers in the field of climate change and health;
- Researchers in the field of implementation science;
- Researchers in the field of EWS development;
- Researchers in the field of epidemiology, social sciences and health economics;
- Policymakers working on impact of climate change on health.

2 FAIR data

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data and other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes, we will use persistent identifiers for

- authors: ORCID ID
- organisations: ROR ID (if available)
- grant: ID grant number of Horizon Europe
- publications: DOI (e.g., peer-reviewed journal article) or ISBN (e.g., WHO publications)
- datasets: at this stage we consider to use Zenodo for sharing the processes data, maybe complemented with discipline-specific datasets
- software: GitHub (e.g. [ClimApp](#))

To be done in next version of the DMP:

- Look into the possibility of using ELIXIR as a repository (because EU recommends this one for life sciences).*
- Consider integration of the ClimApp with Zenodo (because the software code of ClimApp is available on Github, an integration can be made with Zenodo to have a milestone snapshot copy, including identifier).*

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The repository chosen (Zenodo^{2 3}) provides information about at least the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Elements will be provided as defined within the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) Metadata Terms. The metadata model contains the following xml objects:

Table 4: Metadata list

Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Required/Optional
dc:title	Required
dcx:creator	Required
dc:description	Required
dcm:created	Required
dcm:accessrights	Required
dcm:audience	Required
dct:alternative	Optional
dc:subject	Optional
dct:rightholder	Optional
dc:publisher	Optional
dcx:contributor	Optional
dc:type	Optional
dc:format	Optional
dc:identifier	Optional
dc:source	Optional
dc:language	Optional
dcx:relation	Optional
dcx:date	Optional

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, basic discovery metadata will be provided online by the repositories. Upon submission in the data repository, we will provide search keywords to optimize our data for re-use. The same keywords will be used in the publications where possible. The WP2 tasks related to data curation and the heat-health platform have just started. For deliverable 2.1 ‘Environmental-health databases 1’ which is due end of April 2023, metadata including keywords will be defined.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add keywords which are already defined for some of the datasets.

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, we plan to use Zenodo’s harvest module to record metadata in the Zenodo community collection.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Specify how the harvesting and indexing will be done.

² [Zenodo](#)

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

2.2 FAIR data: Making data accessible

2.2.1 Will the data and other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes, data which can be shared openly will be deposited in Zenodo and the software code of the ClimApp-MCH in Github.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Assess whether anonymized health data should be made available in the country where they were collected.

2.2.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data and other research outputs will be deposited?

No, not yet.

2.2.3 Does the repository ensure that the data and other research outputs are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, Zenodo & GitHub register DOIs for all deposited records and research outputs.

2.2.4 Will all data and other research outputs be made openly available?

No, not all data collected by HIGH Horizons will be made openly available (see tables 2 and 3):

- As most HIGH Horizons data are health-related, personal and sensitive, we cannot provide full open access to our datasets. As such, the datasets will not be entirely openly available and conditions will be attached to access the data (= restricted access). We will take actions to limit the restrictions, i.e., to have our datasets "as open as possible, as close as needed", by pseudonymisation/anonymisation of personal data where possible and by agreeing on a limited embargo period (i.e., an embargo period of 5 years after finishing the project). The final decision about how openly accessible the HIGH Horizons datasets will be, will be taken at the end of the project based on the sensitivity of the data, the importance of sharing our data and findings for secondary analyses as well as the quality.
- Non-personal data (e.g. environmental or temperature data) will be made openly available where relevant.
- The code of the adjusted ClimApp software will be made openly available and also software methods used for the heat-health data platform will be shared openly. Both will be deposited in GitHub. During the project the GitHub repository visibility will be restricted to consortium partners only⁴.

Actions to limit the restricted access:

- We aim to make our data openly available as much as possible, however sensitive data included in the environmental-health dataset (see WP2), specifically personal data, will not be made openly available. All individual-level data on women, children, and health workers, using observations, checklists, interview guides, photos, recordings and questionnaires, will be anonymized at the point of data collection. An identification number specific to the study will be used to distinguish each participant and to each facility.

⁴ <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/managing-your-repositorys-settings-and-features/managing-repository-settings/setting-repository-visibility>

- Data from the focus group discussions and key informant interviews will be anonymized (if possible) or pseudonymized.
- Data from the cohort cannot be anonymized as we need to keep the link between personal and health information during the cohort period. However, we are going to pseudonymize these data to secure their privacy.
- Audio files of focus groups or interviews will be destroyed; their transcripts will be made available (restricted access).
- The research teams in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe will remain owner of the samples and data they collect. The provider and the processor will be involved in deciding how to restrict future use of the data in collaboration with the *Data Access Committee*.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add details about the Data Access Committee (if decided to be established), including terms of reference of the committee, criteria to authorize to data,...

2.2.5 Is an embargo applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents)?

Yes, an embargo period will be applied for publications and for the ClimApp software.

2.2.6 If an embargo is applied (see question 2.2.5), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Yes, an embargo period will be applied for as long as necessary.

2.2.7 Will the data and other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes, through Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (https).

2.2.8 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Under the assumption that we will establish a Data Access Committee (DAC): this Committee will consider and process all requests for data access. After the embargo period, access can be granted upon request: the potential user requests access data, which our DAC manages.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Consider how access will be granted after the project.

Investigate if licensing would be an option for the exploitation/sustainability of the ClimApp.

2.2.9 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

In Zenodo metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain, so no authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it. For accessing the data in Zenodo the user may need to be registered and may require login to the user's account. This will depend on the level of access chosen by HIGH Horizons (i.e. closed, open, or embargoed access).⁵

⁵ [Zenodo](#) (access and re-use)

2.2.10 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Yes, the HIGH Horizons considers to set up a Data Access Committee as already referred to in other answers. The Steering Committee will discuss the establishment of a Data Access Committee and its composition in its next meeting.

2.2.11 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.

Yes.

2.2.12 Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, we will apply the metadata standards of Zenodo and ensure that our metadata enable users to access the data.

2.2.13 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

In Zenodo, metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.

Data will remain available and findable for 20 years. Metadata will remain available after 20 years.

2.2.14 Will documentation or reference about any software needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Most of the data are accessible because HIGH Horizons uses common file formats (e.g. .csv, .pdf).

2.3 FAIR data: Making data interoperable

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The data is mainly processed in REDCap, NVivo, Word and Excel by the researchers, but data sharing will be in non-proprietary formats (.pdf, .txt, .csv), which are interoperable. The linked metadata will make the data partly machine readable. Where possible the formats that are preferred by the repositories (i.e. Zenodo, GitHub) will be used.

Standard vocabulary will be used, such as country codes and ISO format of date-time. We will use the standard vocabulary used in clinical trials⁶ and correct applicable clinical ontologies. In addition, we will document all variables throughout the study.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Investigate this question about data interoperability more in the light of the multidisciplinary character of our data (environmental, socio-economic, health)⁷.

⁶ <https://prsinfo.clinicaltrials.gov/definitions.html>

⁷ [FAIRsharing | Standards](#)

2.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies: Will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add any standardized way of recording information that HIGH Horizons comes up with (during the project).

2.3.3 Will your data and other research outputs include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes.

2.4 FAIR data: Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?

The data package deposited in the trusted repository will include README files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.

2.4.2 Will your data and other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data and other research outputs be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

At this stage in the project we don't expect that any dataset will be made available in the public domain (= waiving all rights and permitting all use), only in the trusted repositories.

2.4.3 Will the data and other research output produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, researchers working in climate and health science, health economics, epidemiology, and implementation science can re-use the data.

As mentioned above, the Data Access Committee will grant access to the data collected and produced after consulting the relevant owners and processors. If granted access, licenses will be given depending on the purpose of the secondary analysis. Data will become available after an embargo period of 5 years.

2.4.4 Will the provenance of the data and other research outputs be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, metadata will include information about the provenance of the data, i.e. information about the origin, history or workflow that generated the data, in a way that is compliant with the standards that are used in the community for which the data is curated.

2.4.5 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We will take the following measures to guarantee the quality of the data. Data will be documented on several levels:

- Data level: information about variables and explanation of variable derivations will be documented in the protocols per data collection. Data quality assurance standards (such as ASHRAE for indoor heat exposure measurements) will be applied.
- Study level: detailed procedural and methodological information covering all aspects of the data collection (including questionnaires, codebooks and guidelines) will be shared and agreed upon among all project partners to ensure similarity in data collection methods and data manipulation.
- Reporting level: formats to report (draft) results will be shared and agreed upon among partners.

3 Other research outputs

3.1 Do you have any additional information that was not addressed in previous sections, which you wish to provide regarding other research outputs that are generated or re-used throughout the project?

Yes, other research outputs will be re-used and generated throughout the project such as

- Protocols⁸
- Scripts for data analysis and data modelling
- Software tools (e.g. ClimApp, the AKDN Carbon Footprint tool,...)

The predictive models based on heat stress indices and human heat balance models, algorithms, and source codes of the ClimApp are already openly accessible through GitHub. All coding modifications made during the HIGH Horizons project will be similarly made available as they are produced. The app will be developed in the Open-Source Platform Cordova (Apache Cordova) and built for specific smartphone platforms (e.g., Android). The app is hosted by HIGH Horizons partner ULUND and a subcontractor. The data is saved at another consortium partner DTU. The app is currently owned by the ClimApp Consortium. For teaching and research ClimApp it is free, but for commercial use, the ClimApp consortium must agree. For any new development based on ClimApp, we need to clarify who is the owner.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

- Elaborate this question for protocols and scripts/modelling.*
- Clarify who will be the owner of any new development of ClimApp.*
- Assess how open the further development of ClimApp can be made.*

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 What will the costs be for making data and other research outputs FAIR in your project?

The project will use repositories free of charge for storing and accessing data, and at this stage we do not expect costs for long-term storage and archiving.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

- Discuss internally how ClimApp could be maintained beyond the lifetime of the project and what this would imply in terms of costs.*
- List potential costs for making data and other research outputs FAIR (costs for data storage during the project, cost of data managers,...).*

⁸ <https://www.protocols.io/>

4.2 How will these be covered?

If costs occur during the HIGH Horizons project, these will be covered by the Horizon Europe grant.

4.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The handling of the overall data management, the project's Sharepoint folders and files, the UGent shared network drive "shares" and repositories on behalf of HIGH Horizons, as well as all data management issues related to the project, are the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (Ghent University).

The storage of personal information from questionnaires, informed consent forms and the urine sample data will be managed by the partners in respectively Sweden, Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe.

Responsible local data managers are:

- In Sweden and Denmark (for EWS-related data):
 - PI: Chuansi Gao and Jørn Toftum – resp. ULUND and DTU
 - Study coordinator or Data manager: Hajnalka Bodnar
 - Researcher: Jakob Eggeling
- In Sweden (for health-related data):
 - PI: Nathalie Roos - KI
 - Study coordinator or Data manager: (to be decided)
 - Researcher: (to be decided)
- In Kenya:
 - PI: Zeenat Sulaiman - AKHS
 - Study coordinator-Aquinius Mung'atia
 - Data Manager: James Siku
- In South Africa:
 - PI: Gloria Maimela - WHC
 - Study coordinator or Data manager: Craig Parker
 - Researcher: Dr Fewize Mpondo
- In Zimbabwe:
 - PI: Lillian Chinyanganya - CeSHHAR
 - Study coordinator or Data manager: (to be decided)
 - Researcher: Jetina Tsvaki

4.4 How will long term preservation be ensured?

At this stage we do not expect high costs for long-term preservation, and therefore it is expected that no financial resources are required after project closure.

After project closure decisions about granting access to the open data and research outputs will be taken by the respective partner organisations.

5 Data security

5.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security?

Data security is of major importance in the HIGH Horizons project. The protection of personal data will be ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies, including:

- Through all steps in data gathering, data entry, data cleaning, and analysis, only HIGH Horizons team members will have access to the data. The team will regularly evaluate that people have access only to the information that they strictly need to have access to.
- Each partner will store the data collected on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication. The Ghent University SharePoint will be used for secure storage at the consortium level.
 - UGent: A SharePoint for the HIGH Horizons project was developed and is used only by consortium members. This instance is set up 'on-premise,' meaning that the data are stored within Ghent University. This will ensure that the data are protected in case a device is lost or stolen and guarantees better protection in terms of privacy. SharePoint also provides a backup mechanism for versioning.
 - DTU: Data collected through ClimApp will be stored on a secure server at DTU. Data includes anthropometric information on users (weight, height, age, activity), GIS coordinates and weather data for the location.
- Data storage on local devices will be avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is inevitable, strong passwords will be used, which will be changed regularly.
- Screens will be locked when researchers leave their desks.
- Data will not be sent by email but transferred safely using encryption or secure tools like Filesender or Box.
- When working in a non-digital format: physical access to confidential data will be controlled; for example, field notes or a box of confidential interviews (transcripts, field notes) or completed informed consent forms will not be left unattended behind locked doors.
- When the retention period of confidential data has expired, and there are no further obligations or reasons to keep them, this information will be destroyed safely. This could mean shredding paper before it is disposed of for physical documents. As for digital data, special erasing software will be used.
- The study results may be published for scientific purposes, but anonymity will be protected at all times, and no results will be linked to specific individuals.

Furthermore, the security standards of the data repositories apply.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

- Expand on backup mechanisms for the different platforms.*
- Add information about REDCap.*

5.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, see above.

6 Ethics

6.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Yes, sensitive data will be collected.

- Most steps within the project will have to be approved by the Ethical Committees in the respective countries (including Sweden, Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe – see below). All protocols will include a section on confidentiality.
- Informed consent will be obtained for all activities: the focus group discussions, semi-structured interviews, the survey, urine sample collection, and cohort study participation.
- Samples collected from participants and all personal data will be stored and managed in alignment with the GDPR.
- Informed consent will include sections on data sharing and archiving.
- Data and material transfer agreements will be signed by all parties involved.

The ethics deliverables or IRB filings will be added here when available, as the ethical applications are being prepared at this stage. South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe have Independent National Ethics Committees and/or Institutional Review Boards, and ethical approvals are required for all research involving human subjects. Human samples will be used (urine for health workers to do self-testing of hydration) in Zimbabwe and South Africa for the purpose of responding to the study's objectives. Sample collection will be performed following the ethical regulations of the local ethics committees and European ethics committees.

➤ *The Karolinska Institute – National Ethical Review Board*⁹

The Swedish Ethics Review Authority is a state authority under the Ministry of Education. The purpose of the authority is that it shall achieve increased uniformity and improved efficiency in the processing of applications for ethical review. The authority started its operations on 1 January 2019 and then replaced the regional ethics review boards. The authority is divided into six business regions located in the following locations in Sweden: Gothenburg, Linköping, Lund, Umeå, Uppsala and Stockholm. At each business region, there is at least one medical department and a department that tests other research. In total, the authority has 18 departments. A department consists of ten representatives with a scientific background and five from the public. The chairman of a department must be or have been a judge.

➤ *The University of the Witwatersrand – Research Ethics Committee*¹⁰

The Research Ethics Committee of the University of Witwatersrand is an accredited entity in South Africa and reviews human subjects research of both medical and non-medical content. The University's Ethics Committees are registered with the National Health Research Ethics Council (NHREC) of the Department of Health. All researchers including staff and students conducting any research that may impact directly or indirectly on people, animals or the environment need to seek ethics clearance before any research is conducted, using their online electronic management system.

➤ *The Medical Research Council Zimbabwe*¹¹

The Medical Research Council of Zimbabwe (MRCZ) is a specialized Council of the Research Council of Zimbabwe (RCZ) established in 1974 under the Research Act of 1959 and Government Notice No. 225 of 1974 in order to provide health researchers and institutions which/in which health research is conducted, with independent ethical oversight on research conducted by those researchers or by / within those institutions. The MRCZ is established and supported by the Government of Zimbabwe through the Ministry of Health and Child Welfare. The MRCZ is registered with the US Government's Office of Human Rights Protection (OHRP) as an international ethics committee, it adheres and subscribes to all the international ethics guidelines

⁹ <https://etikprovningmyndigheten.se/>

¹⁰ <https://www.wits.ac.za/research/researcher-support/research-ethics/>

¹¹ [Medical Research Council of Zimbabwe \(mrcz.org.zw\)](http://mrcz.org.zw)

on the conduct of human research which include the Declaration of Helsinki, CIOMS, ICH-GCP and WHO ethics guidelines. It is composed of scientists, medical experts, ethicists, lawyer, and religious community representatives. It is independent in its reflection, advice and decision.

To be done in next version of the DMP:

Add references to ethics deliverables or IRB filings when available.

6.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes.

7 Other issues

7.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes, we consulted the research data management team of Ghent University and data scientists and stewards from consortium partners for additional guidance.

Furthermore we make use of the national and organisational procedures for data management:

- *Ghent University policy framework on Research Data Management*: <https://www.ugent.be/en/research/datamanagement/policies/ghent-university.htm>
- *Data Protect Act (DPA) of Kenya*. The Data Protect Act 2019 and the appointment of a Data Protection Commissioner authorize the recent emphasis on data sharing compliance in Kenya. HIGH Horizons partner AKHS is approaching this compliance more as a network (including Aga Khan University in Kenya) and is even engaging legal experts for the same.
- *Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA)¹² of South Africa*. POPIA serves to promote the protection of personal information processed by public and private bodies; to introduce certain conditions so as to establish minimum requirements for the processing of personal information; to provide for the establishment of an Information Regulator to exercise certain powers and to perform certain duties and functions in terms of this Act and the Promotion of Access to Information Act, 2000; to provide for the issuing of codes of conduct; to provide for the rights of persons regarding unsolicited electronic communications and automated decision making; to regulate the flow of personal information across the borders of the Republic; and to provide for matters connected therewith.

¹² [Protection of Personal Information Act \(POPI Act\) - POPIA](#)